

Crisis Management Approaches of Three Generation Transformational Leaders in the New Normal: A Mix Method Study

Bartolome, Racquel A. and Caballes, Dennis G. 2022

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Abstract:- This pandemic brought every industry to the brink of collapse, but thanks to the presence of leaders who were able to manage their organizations in these chaotic times.

In today's organization, there are predominantly three age generation groups who are handling leadership roles. They are the Baby Boomers aging from 57 to 75 years old, the Generation X aging from 46 to 56, and the millennials aging from 45 to 27 this year 2022.

This study aimed to identify the crisis management approaches of the three age generation groups, to identify if there is a significant relationship between their age generation group and their crisis management approaches and to determine whether there is a significant difference in their crisis management approaches and age generation groups. The research purposely selected participants for this study since it is focused on transformational leaders and leaders from the three age generation groups only.

The research used mixed methods in this study in identifying the crisis management approaches of the three age generation groups by the conduction of interviews, coded and triangulated using the MLQ form 6S. The result of the study relates to the fact that Millennials have an Intellectual Stimulation, Generation X leaders resulted to having Individualized Consideration and the Baby Boomers have Inspirational Motivation in their crises management approaches based on Bennis and Nanus and Sashkin and Sashkin's transformational leadership style. ETA correlation coefficient is used in this study to determine the relationship between the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches. The result only yielded 0.28 which is an indicator of weak correlation, thus the result is no significant relationship.

Kruskal-Wallis H Test is used in this study to determine the significant difference between the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches. The result yielded 7.62 which is higher when tested with the 0.05 in DF of 2 with a value of 5.991.

Keywords:- Transformational Leadership, Age generation Leadership.

I. INTRODUCTION

COVID-19 Pandemic struck the entire world and every industry was affected. One of the most affected industries is the education sector. In this high uncertainty, every industry needed to deliver their programs and or services to the community through effective crisis management in order to ensure the continuity of services. Crisis management is a process designed to prevent or lessen the damage a crisis can inflict on an organization and its stakeholders (Zamoum, K., and Gorpe, T.S., 2018). They wrote that crisis management is actually the process of preventing more damage to happen to a particular organization. Dwidienawati, D., in 2020 stated leadership is one of the key elements to effective crisis management.

Although leadership is a crucial element in addressing crisis, studies say that not all leadership styles are effective in crisis management. According to Forbes (July 17, 2020), transformational leaders are one of the best leaders for managing crisis because of their ability to see the bigger picture to understand the extent of the crisis before executing the response; they also seek the counsel of those closest to the situation and they are able to harness other's know-how to create a logical and adaptive plan.

In today's workforce, we can see four generations predominantly working side by side with each other: Baby Boomers, Gen X and the Millennials and the Generation Alpha or the Gen Z, each with distinct characteristics and leadership potentials that could very well be useful in crisis management. For the purpose of this paper, only the leaders from the Baby Boomers to the millennial groups will be used due to the fact that there may be no to very scarce Gen Z population with leadership positions. Baby Boomers are the generation of the people born between 1946-1964, Gen X is the generation of the people born between 1965-1980, the Millennials are the generation of the people born between 1981-2000 (Debczak, M., 2019).

These three generations present in the workforce and leadership positions in this COVID crisis pandemic particularly the ones that possess transformative leadership style could be one of the reasons why the education industry is now stabilizing amid the persistence of the different variants of the virus. Hence, knowing the relationship between the age generation group of the transformational leaders and their crisis management approaches can help school organizations if not all organizations triumph over difficult situations and changes in systems and management leaderships.

It is in this premise that the researcher would like to further the study of understanding the different crisis management techniques of the transformational leaders in three generation groups. The researcher would like to find out the crisis management approaches of the transformational leaders by carefully analyzing the behaviors and characteristics of the three generation groups that are working behind every success story of different schools in the Philippines in this COVID pandemic; the relationship of the age group of the three generation transformational leaders to their crisis management approaches and the differences in the crisis management approaches of the three generation transformational leaders.

II. METHODOLOGY

Transformational leaders are energetic, charismatic, passionate and driven people. They are those who stimulate and inspire followers to both achieve extraordinary outcomes and in the process, develop their own leadership capacities. (Bass and Riggio, 1985)

James V. Downtown was the one who coined the term Transformational leadership in 1973. It was later added to by Burns in 1978 and proposed that it was only through the strength of the vision and personality that team members could be encouraged to follow. Bass in 1990 added more to the theory by adding ways to measure and rank the success of transformational leadership including the idea of leaders expressing real and focused energy to inspire their followers to be more like them.

Bass also introduced the Four I's of Transformational leadership which are vital to the success of the transformational leaders in transforming followers into becoming better and productive members of the team.

The researcher also draws from the assumption of a possible connection between the transformational leader's age generation group and their leadership style in the new normal. From the study of Bass and Bass in 2008, younger leaders have different cognitive styles than older generations adding to their advanced technological know-how. Several researchers have also gathered several characteristics of younger generation leaders and older generation leaders and their successes but Pintonakis in 2011 that the field of age and leadership was severely under researched. Hence, the researcher would be taking on these studies to attempt to find connections between age and leadership as their primary approach in their crisis management.

Figure 1: Theoretical Framework of the Research

Fig.1

The most suitable methodological framework for this study must address the similarities and differences in the crisis management styles of the three generation age groups as reflected in their transformational leadership attributes in this pandemic. The researcher used the methodological framework shown in Figure 2.

The researcher employed the exploratory sequential design wherein the researcher collected survey interview responses, developed hypotheses and triangulated using quantitative questionnaires.

The researcher made use of a phenomenological approach in the qualitative method aspect of this research. Phenomenology is defined as a theoretical perspective that attempts to generate knowledge about how individuals experience things (Hesse- Biber and Levy 2011). The aim of this Phenomenological qualitative research is to understand and describe the participants' experiences in this pandemic as they see it.

The researcher also applied an inductive approach in this study. Inductive reasoning according to Wikipedia is a method of reasoning in which a body of observations is synthesized to come up with a general principle. In this research, the researcher will aim to analyze the crisis management approaches of the three generation leaders based on their transformation leadership styles followed by triangulation using the MLQ form 6s.

The researcher used the purposive sampling, that is because the assigned leadership style to the researcher is Transformational Leadership. Hence, the researcher qualified participants using USCPrice Interactive Leadership Style Assessment.

This qualitative research study is composed by three transformational leaders in three different generations: The Baby Boomers, The Generation X, and the Millennials.

III. SAMPLING PROCEDURE

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IV. INSTRUMENT AND TECHNIQUES USED

The researcher used the leadership style assessment by University of Southern California consists of 12 interactive questions. The assessment result is computer generated. The assessment is answered by 34 randomly selected school leaders consisting of Academic Coordinators, Principals, Head Teachers and School Directors. The result yielded seven transformational leaders. Among the seven, three are millennial transformative leaders, three Gen X transformative leaders and one Baby boomer transformative leader.

Preparation. The researcher randomly selected transformational leaders that fell into the category of Baby Boomer, Gen X, Millennial using the USCPrice Interactive Leadership Style Assessment. The researcher only chooses one transformational leader from each generation group. Then the researcher collected information from the respondents via virtual interview and survey questions using google forms after receiving their consent.

With the agreement of the researcher's participants, they were given a pseudonym in order to protect their identities. Thus, in this study, we will use the following pseudonyms: Millennial Transformational leader, Gen X Transformational leaders and Baby Boomer Transformational leader..

Validation. The researcher then crafted interview questions for the selected transformational leaders to answer. The researcher will also use the MLQ Form 6S to triangulate the responses of the transformational leaders. Triangulation is necessary to confirm the correctness of my coding or analysis of the participants' responses and to ensure that their results are congruent with the results of my interview.

Pilot Testing. In this manner, the researcher selected some of the participants who also belong to the transformational leadership styles but are excess of what the researcher needed. The researcher also floated the interview questions to them to test the clarity of the interview questions and to see if the participants will understand the interview questions the same way the participants of the pilot testing did.

When the researcher was satisfied with the result of the reliability and validity of the interview questions, the researcher is now ready to float the interview and triangulation questions to the participants.

Administration and Retrieval. After securing the participants consent form, the research made arrangements with the participants to schedule the interview. The researcher made google forms for the participants to answer in connection to the questions that will be asked during the interview. The participants were also given another google form containing the MLQ Form 6S. This form is for the triangulation of their responses.

When the forms were received, the researcher coded the interview responses of the participants several times to check the correctness of the coding. Afterwhich, the researcher analyzed the results of the participants' MLQ Form 6S.

V. DATA GATHERING PROCEDURES

After receiving the consent of the respondents, the researcher sent out interview questionnaires to the transformational leaders, after which, the researcher conducted interviews with the respondents. The researcher also sent out the MLQ form 6S with the questionnaires using google form for easy tabulation of the results.

VI. TREATMENT OF DATA

To answer the first question, the researcher coded the interview responses employing deductive approach. After the initial coding, the researcher then organized the codes into categories after which the researcher was able to identify themes.

After the coding, the researcher conducted triangulation of the results using the MLQ form 6S. Since the study only employed one transformational leader in each generation group, the researcher used ETA correlation coefficient to find out the answer to whether there is a significant relationship between the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches.

To answer the research question of whether there is a significant difference in the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches, since the research only used one respondent in each age group, the researcher used Kruskal Wallis H-test.

The researcher employed inferential correlation to the relationship between the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches. ETA correlation coefficient is used to determine if a relationship exists between an interval variable and a categorical variable. Kruskal-Wallis H test is a rank-based nonparametric test that is used to determine if there is a significant difference between two or more groups.

VII. RESULTS

After a series of survey questionnaires and interviews, the researcher was able to gather the following responses from the participants. The responses were then attempted to be coded and categorized as follows:

PARTICIPANT	GENDER	AGE	POSITION	YEARS IN THE POSITION
MTL KC	Female	26	English Specialist/HOD	2 yrs
GXTL GIEANN	Female	49	Preschool HOD	7 yrs
BBTL BIBOY	Female	58	Academic Coordinator/Principal	6 yrs

Table 1: Participants Profile

After a series of survey questionnaires and interviews, the researcher was able to gather the following responses from the participants. The responses were then attempted to be coded, and categorized into two themes: behavior and characteristics. After further analysis the themes were broken into different categories. Behavior was then categorized into task-oriented behavior, relationship-oriented behavior and

personality-oriented behavior. Characteristics were categorized into Intellectual Stimulation, Individualized consideration and Inspirational Motivation. These emergent themes were believed to have shaped the similarities and differences in the crisis management approaches of the three generation transformational leaders.

Question 1: In this COVID-19 pandemic, what were the crisis management approaches of a transformational leader in each generation group?

The three generation leaders have some similarities and differences in their crisis management approaches. In terms of technical skills, MTL KC is the most technologically advanced among the three transformational leaders as indicated in the tools she used in the checking, observation and evaluation of her team’s work and outputs. She is also the only one who is able to provide technical support to her team in this pandemic. In terms of personal support, GXTL GIEANN and BBTL BIBOY are able to provide personal support to their team since they are more experienced. GXTL GIEANN provided more personal support to her team in terms of providing individualized care to her team by constant checking via messenger and sending food deliveries. BBTL BIBOY on the other hand provided a more face to face personal support to her team because they report to school for work even in the pandemic due to their lack of strong internet connections in their individual houses.

MTL KC is more of an INTELLECTUAL STIMULATION as her crisis management approach in this pandemic as reflected in her responses. An Intellectual Stimulation Transformational leader according to Annette Towler in 2019 in the CQ Net C article, is a leader that challenges assumptions, risk takers, and solicits followers’ ideas, innovative and the ones who are independent and encourages independence, fosters and helps develop future leaders. MTL KC exhibits the characteristics and the behavior of an Intellectual Stimulation Transformational leader.

GXTL GIEANN’s responses reflect an INDIVIDUALIZED CONSIDERATION transformational leader. Her responses include providing individualized support and care to her team, she is more considerate of her team’s own strengths and weaknesses thus she is able to utilize them in her crisis management. An Individualized Consideration Transformational Leader is a leader that attends to each individual’s needs and is a mentor and a guide to them. (Towler, 2019). She is aware of the unique talents and abilities of her team and is able to support and guide them to her leadership’s advantage.

BBTL BIBOY’s responses reflect that of an INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION transformational leader. Her responses are more nurturing and charismatic, a mark of a motivational leader. Her responses include her being motherly and more focused on leading by example to show how things are done that enabled her and her team to cope with the challenges brought about by the pandemic. Annette Towler in 2019 states that an INSPIRATIONAL MOTIVATION Transformational Leader is a leader that articulates an appealing vision and motivates others to perform beyond

expectations. She mentioned in one of her responses that she motivated her team not to give up and not to focus on the negative thus now, they are able to do things with ease unlike in the beginning of the pandemic.

In their responses, the participants showed similarities in some behavioral aspects of their crisis management approaches that include being caring, loving and understanding. They all also answered that they learned to be resilient and adaptive to the needs of time. They all focused on mentoring their team members, being a guide to them and provided an area for communication.

A difference highlighted in their responses is that they differ in confidence. MTL KC is less confident in her leadership while GXTL GIEANN and BBTL BIBOY are more confident in their leadership. One assumption may be due to the age perception of the participants. MTL KC mentioned that her age is one of her limitations in terms of soliciting respect and obedience from her team; on the other hand, GXTL GIEANN and BBTL BIBOY mentioned that their ages are their asset in their leadership due to their experiences and maturity; they are able to share their organizational skills thus giving their team a more focused and prepared environment.

Question 2: Is there a significant relationship between the transformational leaders’ age generation group and their crisis management in the new normal?

The researcher employed the use of ETA correlation coefficient in determining the relationship between the two variables. After manually calculating the ETA correlation coefficient, the researcher was able to gather the result as shown in Table 2.

Transformational Leader	age	Idealize Influence	Inspirational Motivation	Intellectual Stimulation	Individualize Consideration	Idealize Influence	Inspirational Motivation	Intellectual Stimulation	Individualize Consideration	Total
TL KC	26	7	10	12	8	2.79	0.11	7.13	1.77	
TL Biboy	58	11	12	10	11	5.43	5.43	0.45	2.79	
TL Gieann	49	8	7	6	9	0.45	7.13	11.09	0.11	
	Total	26	29	28	28	8.67	12.67	18.67	4.67	44.68
	Average	8.67	9.67	9.33	9.33					
Y =	9.25									
SS(BG) =	1.58									
SS(M) =	44.68									
SS(T) =	46.26									
ETA =	0.18									
	No significant correlation									

Table 2: Test for ETA Correlation Coefficient

Although based on the interviews and the interpretation of the MLQ form 6S, the results of the respondents are congruent, the relationship between their age generation group and crisis management approaches is not significant probably because the sample used is too small for the test. The result only yielded 0.28 which is an indicator of weak correlation, thus the result is no significant relationship.

Question 3: Is there a significant difference between the transformational leaders’ age generation group and their crisis management approaches in the new normal?

After employing the Kruskal-Wallis test in determining the difference between groups, the results showed that there is a significant difference in the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches as shown in the manual tabulation and calculation of the responses in Table 3.

	Idealize Influence	Rank	Inspirational Motivation	Rank	Intellectual Stimulation	Rank	Individualized Consideration	Rank
Millennial	7	2.5	10	9.5	12	11.5	8	4.5
Gen X	8	4.5	7	7.5	6	1	9	6
Baby Boomer	11	9.5	12	11.5	10	7.5	11	9.5
HStat =	7.62							
DF =	2							
0.05 =	5.991							

Table 3: Kruskal-Wallis H test

The result yielded 7.62 which is higher when tested with the 0.05 in DF of 2 with a value of 5.991.

After reviewing the results of coded interview further, the researcher found out the differences in their crisis management approaches in terms of the following parameters:

A. CURRICULUM IMPLEMENTATION

The three generation leaders exhibited very minimal differences in terms of their curriculum implementation. All of them responded that they follow the DepEd MELC, observe DepED guidelines in assessments and mandated activities. All of the participants mentioned that they are all able to create creative virtual events to their schools as part of their curriculum implementation. Among the three, only BBTL BIBOY mentioned that they are in close connection to the DepEd Division office and constantly updates her team of the guidelines in the DepEd memos.

B. MANAGEMENT OF DATA AND PROCESSES

The three generation transformational leaders reflected similar responses in their management of data and processes in this pandemic. All made use of their available resources, online tools in their monitoring, checking and ensuring that classes are going as planned. They all mentioned the use of GC (Group Chats) using Messenger, Emails, and Edmodo. MTL KC and GXTL GIEANN mentioned the use of Microsoft Teams and BBTL BIBOY mentioned the use of Google Meet as their communication platform for monitoring.

They mentioned that they all observe classes and provided feedback after. Among the three, only MTL KC used a digital tracker as part of her digital record to evaluate her team. GXTL GIEANN confessed that she still uses manual recording because of its ease of usage and ease of verification even when she is not online. BBTL BIBOY mentioned that she uses mix methods in monitoring and checking. She mentioned that she checks outputs manually and records digitally.

C. COMMUNICATION

The participants exhibited slightly different responses in their approaches to communication during the pandemic. MTL KC mentioned that she only made use of emails, teams and messenger as her lines of communication. Among the three, she is more virtual in her approach to communication.

She did not mention the use of SMS or phone calls to communicate to her team. Although she kept her lines of communication open, she mentioned that she does not communicate to her team after working hours in respect to their personal boundaries.

GXTL GIEANN and BBTL BIBOY are somehow more connected to their teams as compared to MTL KC as they mentioned they do phone calls to communicate with their team and sometimes meet their team face to face when they want to make their statement mark. GXTL GIEANN mentioned that she ensures she meets her team regularly and constantly asks them how they are doing. BBTL BIBOY mentioned that she visits her team's classroom since they report to school for work to check them out and to see how she can help or even when she needs technical help from them.

D. STAFF WELL-BEING

All mentioned they provided a work-life balance schedule with their teams. Their responses showed that they value their team and they are able to provide the essential help their team needs in this pandemic.

MTL KC provided space to her team, that is, she ensured that after work hours, her team was able to rest and be able to face their personal lives beyond school. Fow MTL KC, providing her team ample time to do their own things and not pressure them to accomplish their tasks is her way to provide her staff a good work-life balance that she knows can help them sustain their mental health in this pandemic.

GXTL GIEANN on the other hand differs in providing her staff with the well-being in this pandemic. Her approaches include sending them food deliveries, checking them out via calls, chats and even asking them to eat out with her from time to time. She also mentioned that she is more personal in telling her team to look after themselves this pandemic and ensure to have work-life balance.

BBTL BIBOY's approach of providing her team with well-being is the most different of all. To her, helping her team prepare and complete their tasks would ensure a healthy life for them because according to her, what stresses her is the lack of preparation and unfinished work. Hence, she makes sure that she is able to help her team complete their tasks on time.

The similarity all participants exhibited in this aspect is that all of them are prayerful. They included that they pray for their team as a way to help them with their spiritual connection with God.

E. PERSONAL WELL-BEING

The participants exhibited some similarities and differences in this aspect of their approach to crisis management. MTL KC Mentioned that to help herself, she made sure that she is able to read books, binge watch Netflix and K-drama as part of her de-stressing in this pandemic. GXTL GIEANN mentioned that she spends time to bond with her son and husband, do beauty care through salon visits, do some grocery shopping and strolling with her family to keep her well-being in this pandemic. BBTL BIBOY said that he studied and learned to cope with the challenges of the

pandemic to help herself. To her, preparation and planning helps her mental health and de-stress her. She did not mention exercising or eating healthy as part of her well-being maintenance, rather, her responses are more focused on ensuring she knows what she will answer her team should they ask them about certain things. To her being prepared is her approach to having a healthy self.

MTL KC and GXTL GIEANN showed some similarities in keeping themselves healthy during this pandemic by exercising and eating healthy. They also mentioned they do socializing as part of their self management.

The three however are similar in including prayer as part of their self management in this pandemic. They made sure they are able to pray and seek God for guidance to keep their spiritual lives healthy.

VIII. SUMMARY

In summary, this study could be employed for large scale study of the same purpose. The researcher was able to gather pertinent information and insight in floating the study to a bigger population.

- The study is only conducted to three participants with different age generation groups: millennial, generation x and baby boomers.
- The study employed mixed methods in soliciting answers for question 1 and supplementing answers in question 3.
- The study is for validation purposes only in preparation for a large-scale study of the researcher for her dissertation.
- The researcher was not able to find a relationship between the age generation group and crisis management approaches of the transformational leaders in this study but was able to find significant differences in the crisis management approaches and their age generation groups.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

- The researcher identified the crisis management approach of the three generation transformational leaders to their leadership styles.
 - Millennial Transformational Leaders are found to be more of an intellectual stimulator leader, hence, the researcher sees that millennial transformational leaders are more logical, technical and less personal in their crisis management approach.
 - Generation X Transformational Leaders are found to be more of an individualized consideration transformational leader as their crisis management approach, hence the researcher sees that Gen X transformational leaders are more personal, somewhat technical and more people oriented in their crisis management approach.
 - Baby Boomer Transformational Leaders are found to be one of the inspirational motivation transformational leaders. Their age is simply her motivating factor that ensures a more nurturing approach, hence, the research sees that Baby Boomers are the least technically inclined among the three generational leaders but is the most motivating of all as they inspire people to learn and be prepared and that if they can, so can they.

- There is no significant relationship between the transformational leaders' age generation group and their crisis management approaches in the new normal.
- There is a significant difference in the transformational leaders' crisis management approaches in the new normal.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Since the study is made for the validation purpose of the researcher's dissertation material, the study must adhere to purposive sampling since the study requires transformational leaders from specific age generation groups.
- Future researchers must use a bigger sample of the population to be able to gather better results. Non-parametric design for this research will not yield accurate results since the number of participants is too small to create an accurate theory.
- Future researchers can try to employ the design using different leadership styles to prove the accuracy of the statistical treatment and instruments used in this research.

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